

Research article

Morpho-anatomical traits, DNA barcode and phytochemical screening of *Aglaonema cochinchinense*

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Abstract: *Aglaonema cochinchinense* is a rare species. It is found in some limited areas of southern Vietnam, Thailand and Cambodia. The present study provides its morphological, anatomical, phytochemical characteristics, and DNA barcode for the first time. The results from this study hold promise for using as a monographic literature in the identification of the medicinal plants as well as further application of this species in medicinal field and other related fields.

Keywords: *Aglaonema cochinchinense*, anatomy, *matK*, morphology, phytochemistry

Introduction

The genus *Aglaonema* consists of herbaceous plants belonging to Araceae family. It comprises about 22 species distributed in southern China, southeastern Asia, New Guinea, Indonesia, and northeastern India (Nicolson, 1969; Hay, 1998; Li & Boyce, 2010; Van et al., 2020). The dense and humid forests or tidal mudflats (i.e. *Aglaonema griffithii*) are the characteristic habitats of the members of this genus (Nicolson,

1969; Hay, 1998; Li & Boyce, 2010; Van et al., 2020). Taxonomic studies separated *Aglaonema* genus into two sections, *Chamaecaulon* and *Aglaonema*, using their morphological characteristics. Accordingly, the first section contained only two species such as *A. brevispathum* and *A. costatum* which they are characterised by having: branching and creeping stem, petiole sheath shorter than 1/5 petiole length, cataphylls subtending the petioles (Nicolson, 1969; Van, 2017; Nguyen, 2017). Meanwhile, the later section included

all the remaining species of the genus that they are indicated by the erect stem, infrequently decumbent and branching, petiole sheath longer than 1/5 petiole length, cataphylls rarely subtending the petioles (Nicolson, 1969; Van, 2017; Nguyen, 2017). Recently, based on its morphological and molecular evidences, *Aglaodorum griffithii* was transferred to *Aglaonema* genus and it was recognised as a synonym of *Aglaonema griffithii* (Van et al., 2020).

Aglaonema cochinchinense Engler was described for the first time in 1915 of which the type specimen was collected from Cochinchina (Engler, 1915). To date, this species is found in some limited areas of southern Thailand, Cambodia and southern Vietnam (Nicolson, 1969; Van, 2017; Nguyen, 2017) and it is for reason that *A. cochinchinense* is a rare species with restricted distribution and the studies on this plants are limited. Previous study have used *A. cochinchinense* as a tool to develop the light-emitting plants by inoculating *Vibrio campbellii* RMT1 on the rhizospheric zone of this species (Kanjapokin et al., 2024). In our prior work, “Phylogenetic position of *Aglaodorum* Schott (Araceae-Aroideae-Aglaonemateae)”, two molecular regions, *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF* IGS, of *A. cochinchinense* were also provided and deposited in NCBI database with the accession numbers of MN844021 and MN844009, respectively (Van et al., 2020). The present study, thus, provides the detail morphological, anatomical, *matK* region, and the phytochemical screening of *Aglaonema cochinchinense* for the first time.

Materials and methods

Plant materials

The samples of *A. cochinchinense* was collected from natural secondary forest in Phuoc Vinh commune, Chau Thanh District, Tay Ninh Province, Vietnam, on 25 April 2024. The vouchered specimen, NPN-1121, was deposited at the Herbarium of University of Science, Vietnam National University-HCMC (PHH). In addition, the specimen of *Aglaonema simplex* from our prior work (Van et al., 2017a) was collected from Tra Don commute, Nam Tra My District, Quang Nam Province, Vietnam, on 7 April 2015 of which the vouchered specimen (Van H.T 69) was deposited at the Herbarium of Southern Institute of Ecology,

Institute of Applied Materials Science, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology (SGN).

Morphological characteristics

The guidelines of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew was used to identify the studied sample (Bridson & Forman, 1999). The vegetative and reproductive characteristics of *A. cochinchinense* and *A. simplex* were compared with those of previous reports on *Aglaonema* genus (Nicolson, 1969; Hay, 1998; Pham, 2000; Li & Boyce, 2010; Van, 2027; Nguyen, 2017; Van et al., 2020).

Anatomical characteristics

The root, leaf, and rhizome of *A. cochinchinense* were cut into thin slices and soak Javel solution to remove the unwanted components in plant tissue. The iodine green-carmin double staining method was used to stain the microscopic specimens. The distilled water was used to wash these specimens and they was preserved in 10% glycerol (Truong et al., 2007). The samples were observed and taken the picture with the Olympus BX53 Digital Upright Microscope.

DNA extraction, PCR reaction and sequencing data analysis

DNA Gene Jet Plant Genomic DNA Purification Mini Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was used to isolate the total DNA of the *A. cochinchinense*. The *matK* region of the studied species was amplified using a Mastercycler PCR machine (Eppendorf, Germany) with the components as following: 12.5 µL master mix (Phu Sa Company, Vietnam), 1.25 µL of each forward and reverse primer at 10 µM concentration; 9.0 µL deionised water and 1.0 µL DNA sample. PCR cycling conditions were 5 minutes at 95°C; 35 cycles of 1 minute at 94°C, 1 minute at 56°C and 1 minute 30 seconds at 72°C; a final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes. PCR products were purified and sequenced at the Nam Khoa BioTek Company (Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam). The FinchTV and Seaview softwares were used to process the *matK* regions of the studied species. These sequences were aligned using the Basic Local

Table 1. The methods used to identify main groups of metabolites of *A. cochinchinense*.

Phytochemical	Reagent	Positive reaction	References
Phenolics and tannins	2 ml extract + 2 ml H ₂ O + 2–3 drops FeCl ₃ 5%	color change to brownish to blackish green	Deka et al. (2017)
Alkaloids	2 ml extract + 3–4 drops Wagner reagent	reddish-brown precipitate formation	Bodi et al. (2014)
Flavonoids	2 ml extract + 2 ml Pb(COOH) ₂ 10%	yellow precipitate formation	Nguyen et al. (2017)
Saponins	2 ml extract + 10 ml H ₂ O + 2-minute ebullition	foam formation	Shaikh & Patil (2020)
Terpenoids and steroids	5 ml extract + 2 ml CCl ₄ + 3 ml Sulfuric acid concentrate	colour change to brownish-red	Llauradó et al. (2013)
Coumarins	2 ml extract + 3 ml NaOH (10%)	colour change to yellow or dark yellow	Vo et al. (2017)

Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) on NCBI (National Center Biotechnology Information).

Extraction procedures

The fresh rhizome, root, flower, and leaves of *A. cochinchinense* were dried at 50°C then grinded into powdered. Five grams of each material was subjected to extraction using 99% ethanol (1:30, w/w) for 8 hours. Subsequently, the first supernatant was collected through filtration. This extraction procedure was repeated two times for the resulting residue and all supernatant fractions were combined.

Qualitative analysis of secondary metabolites of *A. cochinchinense*

The presence of different phytochemicals were determined by qualitative methods presented in Table 1.

Quantitative analysis of secondary metabolites of *A. cochinchinense*

Total polyphenol content

Take 0.1 mL of sample into a test tube, then add 1.8 mL of Folin – Ciocalteu solution, shake well and leave for 5 minutes for Folin – Ciocalteu to react completely with polyphenols. Add 1.2 mL of 15% Na₂CO₃ solution to create alkaline pH, and finally add

distilled water to make 10 ml. Cover, shake well, then incubate in dark conditions for 90 minutes and then measure photoluminescence at wavelength $\lambda = 734$ nm. The control tube was replaced with distilled water. Total polyphenol contents of the studied samples were calculated according to the gallic acid standard curve. Total polyphenol content was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalent (GAE). Based on the photometric results and standard curve graph, the total polyphenol concentration in the studied sample was determined (Kadarani et al., 2015). Total polyphenol content was calculated according to the formula:

$$TPC (mg GAE/g DW) = C_x \times \frac{V}{10^3} \times \frac{100}{a \times (100 - W)} \times K$$

where: C_x: the total polyphenol concentration in the extract calculated from the standard curve (ppm); V: sample volume (ml); a: initial sample mass (g); W: humidity (%); K: dilution factor; 10³: conversion factor.

Total flavonoid content

Take 1 ml of sample into a test tube, add 0.3 mL of 5% NaNO₂ solution and shake well and leave for 5 minutes. Then add 0.3 mL of 10% AlCl₃ solution, shake well and leave for 5 minutes, add 2 mL of 1M NaOH solution, shake well and add 6.4 mL of distilled water to make 10 mL and then measure photometrically at wavelength $\lambda = 510$ nm. The control tube was replaced with distilled water. Total

flavonoid content was expressed as milligrams of quercetin acid equivalent (QE). Based on the photometric results and standard curve graph, the total flavonoid concentration in the studied sample was determined (Sen et al., 2013). Total flavonoid content was calculated according to the formula:

$$TFC (mg QE/g DW) = C_x \times \frac{V}{10^3} \times \frac{100}{a \times (100 - W)} \times K$$

where: C_x : the total flavonoid concentration in the extract calculated from the standard curve (ppm); V : sample volume (mL); a : initial sample mass (g); W : humidity (%); K : dilution factor; 10^3 : conversion factor.

Total triterpene content

Take 1 ml of extracted sample into a test tube, add 0.2 mL of 5% acetic acid and 1.2 mL of perchloric acid ($HClO_4$), mix and incubate at 70°C for 15 minutes then cool quickly for 2 minutes. The mixture was added with 2.6 mL of ethyl acetate to make 5 mL and photometrically measured at 550 nm wavelength. The control tube was replaced with 5% acetic acid. Total triterpenoid content was expressed as milligrams of oleanoic acid equivalent (OAE). Based on the photometric results and standard curve graph, the total triterpene concentration in the studied sample was determined (Chen et al., 2007). Total triterpene content was calculated according to the formula:

$$TTC (mg OAE/g DW) = C_x \times \frac{V}{10^3} \times \frac{100}{a \times (100 - W)} \times K$$

where: C_x : the total triterpenoid concentration in the extract calculated from the standard curve (ppm); V : sample volume (ml); a : initial sample mass (g); W : humidity (%); K : dilution factor; 10^3 : conversion factor.

Results

Taxonomic treatment

Aglaonema cochinchinense Engl. 1915. Pflanzenr. 64 (IV. 23 Dc): 16; Gagnep. 1942. Fl. Gén. Indoch. 6: 1128; Nicolson, 1969. Smiths. Contr. Bot.1: 37, Fig. 4; Phamh. 1993. Illustr. Fl. Vietn. 3: 434, fig. 8296; id. 2000. Illustr. Fl. Vietn. 3: 348; fig. 9104; Govaert et

al. 2002. World Checkl. Bibliogr. Arac. 55; V.D. Nguyen, 2005. in N.T. Ban Checkl. Pl. Vietn. 3: 872; V.D. Nguyen, 2006. Arac. Vietn.: 75; P.C. Boyce et al. 2012. Fl. Thail. 11: 113. (Fig. 1).

Synonym: *Aglaonema cambodianum* Gagnep. 1941. Notul. Syst. 9: 116.

Herb evergreen, 30–50 cm high, 3–4 internodes, 1.5–2.5 cm long, 2–2.5 cm in diameter. Rhizome underground, cylindrical, up to 20 cm long, 1.5–2 cm in diameter with many long and stout roots, 20–25 cm long, 0.5–1 cm in diameter. Leaves many, 2–3 growing from the base of each internode. Petioles 8–14 cm long, ca. 0.3 cm at base, ca. 0.8 cm at apex, dark green; leaf blade oval or elliptical, 20–24 cm long, 8–12 cm wide, rounded base, slightly pointed tip, dark green above, pale green beneath, midrib convex near the axis, concave on the abaxial side, the lateral veins diverging from the midrib and toward margin. Inflorescence 2–4, emerging from petiole axils; peduncle 10–12 cm long and ca. 0.3 cm in diameter, dark green; spathe shorter than spadix, dark green on the outside, pale on the inside, 3.2–3.5 cm long, 1–1.2 cm wide, oval, straight, without distinguishing between the tube and limb; spadix longer than spathe, cylindrical, 4–4.5 cm long, pedunculate ca. 0.4 cm long; female part ca. 0.5 cm long, ca. 0.8 cm in diameter with 1–2 whorls of flowers, flowers loosely arranged; stigma is round, bright yellow when young, dark brown when mature, shiny, diameter 2–2.5 mm; style short, ca. 0.5 mm long; ovary round, ca. 2 mm in diameter, greenish white, 1-locular, with 1 basal ovule, ca. 0.5 mm in diameter, opaque white; male part much longer than female part, 3.5–4 cm long, 1–1.2 cm wide, stamens densely arranged, light yellow, anthers open with apical holes. Fruit ovoid, long 8–12 mm, 4–6 mm in diameter, green when young, red when mature.

Type: Pierre s.n. (holotype: B; isotype: P), Cochinchina, 1915.

Habitat: the species grows on the litter layer of limestone under the canopy of evergreen forest.

Distribution: Ninh Thuan, Tay Ninh, An Giang provinces, Vietnam. This species was also found in Thailand and Cambodia.

Pairwise sequence alignment of *matK* regions among *Aglaonema cochinchinense* and *Aglaonema simplex*

In this study, the *matK* region of *A. cochinchinense* was sequenced for the first time which its length was

Fig. 1. *Aglaonema cochinchinense* Engl. A. Whole plant. B. Leaf blade. C. Inflorescence. D. Spathe. E. Spadix. F. Stamens. G. Longitudinal section of ovary. H. Fruits. I. Longitudinal and cross sections of fruits.

735 bps. In addition, the *matK* region of *A. simplex*, a morphologically resembled species with *A.*

cochinchinense, obtained from our prior work (Van et al. 2017a) was also used in this study. The *matK* re-

Fig. 3. The cross-section of root. A. sector of the cross-section. B. Cortex (1: piliferous layer, 2: exodermis, 3: cortical parenchyma). C. Stele (1: cortical parenchyma, 2: endodermis with Casparian strip, 3: pericycle, 4: phloem, 5: medullary ray, 6: protoxylem, 7: metaxylem, 8: medullary parenchyma).

regions of *A. cochinchinense* and *A. simplex* were firstly deposited in NCBI database with the accession numbers of PP886110 and PP886111, respectively. In this study, thus, the pairwise alignment of the *matK* regions between these species was conducted (Fig. 2). Accordingly, there were 5 non-homologous positions (158, 166, 389, 457, and 689) between two regions.

Micromorphology of the *Aglaonema cochinchinense*

Roots (Fig. 3)

The cross-section of root is nearly circular and divided into 2 distinct areas, the cortical region accounts for 5/6 of the radius of cross-section, a pith region accounts for 1/6 of the radius. Cortex: the piliferous layer consists of a layer of irregular, polygonal cells with distorted walls impregnated with phellem and scattered with root hairs. The exodermis

includes 3–5 layers of polygonal cells, walls impregnated with thin phellem or cellulose, arranged haphazardly and closely together. The cortical parenchyma are round or polygonal cells with cellulose walls, arranged haphazardly, leaving leaving small polygonal or intercellular spaces. The endodermis with Casparian strip is clear with one layer of cells, nearly rectangular. Stele: the pericycle consists of a layer of flattened polygonal cells, interspersed with endodermal cells and cellulose walls. The vascular bundles are concentrated right under the pericycle layer, including 13–17 phloem bundles and 13–17 protoxylem bundles arranged alternately on a ring. Phloem bundles are arranged in small oval clusters, polygonal cells, cellulose walls. The protoxylem bundle consists of 2–4 xylem vessels, polygonal shape, walls impregnated with xylem, radially differentiated. The metaxylem includes 12–14 vessels, larger than the protoxylem, unequal size, not in contact or in contact just below the protoxylem bundle in the per-

Fig. 4. The cross-section of rhizome. A. Cortex (1: phellem; 2: parenchyma, 3: spiny shaped calcium oxalate crystals). B. Stele (1: parenchyma, 2: phloem, 3: xylem, 4: vascular bundle). C. Calcium oxalate crystals (1: needle-shaped, 2: spiny-shaped). D. Vascular bundle.

imedullary area. The medullary rays consist of 1–2 rows of polygonal parenchyma cells between the phloem and xylem bundles, cellulose wall. The medullary parenchyma cells are polygonal, cellulose wall, arranged closely together.

Rhizome (Fig. 4)

The cross-section of rhizome is nearly circular. The phellem includes many layers of flattened rectangular cells, arranged in radial rows. The phelloderm has 1–2 layers of rectangular cells, cellulose wall. The parenchyma has many layers of nearly circular cells, cellulose walls, arranged with leaving small polygonal or intercellular spaces. There are many vascular bundles, scattered throughout the medullary

parenchyma, usually individual bundles with phloem above and xylem below or arranged in clusters of 2 bundles; each cluster has a phloem in the middle and xylem vessels arranged on opposite sides. There are 2 types of calcium oxalate crystals: (1) the spiny spherical crystals scattered throughout parenchyma area, (2) the needle-shaped crystals adhered in bundles in elongated cells.

Leaves (Fig. 5)

Midrib is concave on the upper surface, convex on the lower surface. The epidermal cells have a thin layer of cuticle; stomata are scattered throughout both layers of the epidermis. The angular collenchyma arranged in clusters, 3–6 layers of upper epidermis and 6–7 lay-

Fig. 5. The cross-section of leaf. A. Leaf blade (1: upper epidermis, 2: parenchyma, 3: lower epidermis). B. Petiole (1: parenchyma, 2: vascular bundle, 3: collenchyma, 4: lower epidermis). C. Stele of petiole (1: parenchyma, 2: vascular bundle).

ers of lower epidermis, polygonal cells, cellulose walls. There are 2 types of parenchyma, (1) close to the collenchyma are 3–10 layers of medullary parenchyma that includes nearly round and small cells; (2) the remaining area is spongy parenchyma, usually a series of cells connected together to create many irregular, large and small intercellular spaces. These intercellular spaces gradually become smaller and disappear when approaching the lower epidermis. The vascular bundles have irregular sizes and are scattered in parenchyma; each bundle consists of xylem above and phloem below; xylem consists of 2–8 irregular xylem veins; phloem is polygonal cells. Calcium oxalate crystals have two forms: spiny spheres scattered throughout parenchyma; needle-shaped adherent into bundles within large, oval cells. Leaf blade: the epidermis is the same as the midrib, the lower epidermal cells are larger than the upper epidermal cells. The spongy parenchyma has polygonal cells with many large intercellular spaces. Petiole: the cross-section has the same characteristics as the

midrib. Sheath: the cross-section has two thin wings on both sides.

Qualitative phytochemistry of *A. cochinchinense*

The qualitative phytochemistry of the ethanol extracts isolated from rhizome, root, flower, and leaf of *Aglaonema cochinchinense* were presented in the Table 2. Overall, all four organs of this plant contained various bioactive compounds, including phenolic, tannin, alkaloid, flavonoid, saponin, terpenoid, steroid, and coumarin.

Quantitative phytochemical content of *A. cochinchinense*

Table 3 shows the total of triterpene, flavonoid, and polyphenol contents of the *A. cochinchinense*. Accordingly, the rhizome possessed the most quantita-

Table 2. Qualitative analysis of secondary metabolites of *Aglaonema cochinchinense*.

Metabolites	Rhizome	Root	Flower	Leaf
Phenolics	+++	+	+	++
Tannins	+++	+	+	++
Alkaloids	+	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+++	++	++	+++
Saponins	++	+	++	++
Terpenoids	+++	++	+	+++
Steroids	+++	++	+	+++
Coumarins	+++	++	++	++

Note: (+) Less, (++) Medium, (+++) Very abundant.

Table 3. Phytochemical content of *A. cochinchinense*.

Phytochemical contents	Rhizome	Root	Flower	Leaf
TTC (mg OAE/g DW)	41.831 ± 0.016	1.731 ± 0.009	0.323 ± 0.008	3.464 ± 0.017
TFC (mg QE/g DW)	68.517 ± 0.030	17.410 ± 0.013	30.271 ± 0.007	32.323 ± 0.006
TPC (mg GAE/g DW)	51.342 ± 0.095	3.552 ± 0.008	8.982 ± 0.033	11.642 ± 0.038

Note: TTC: total triterpene content, TFC: total flavonoid content, TPC: total polyphenol content.

tive contents with the total of triterpene, flavonoid, and polyphenol contents of 41.831 mg OAE/g DW, 68.517 mg QE/g DW, and 51.342 mg GAE/g DW, respectively, followed by leaf (3.464 mg OAE/g DW, 32.323 mg QE/g DW, 11.642 mg GAE/g DW), flower (0.323 mg OAE/g DW, 30.271 mg QE/g DW, 8.982 mg GAE/g DW), and root (1.731 mg OAE/g DW, 17.410 mg QE/g DW, 3.552 mg GAE/g DW).

Discussion

Studies separated *Aglaonema* genus into two sections, *Chamaecaulon* and *Aglaonema*. The first section contained only two species such as *A. brevispathum* and *A. costatum* whereas the later one included all the remaining species of the genus (Nicolson, 1969; Van 2017; Nguyen 2017). *A. cochinchinense* and *A. simplex* were classified in the section *Aglaonema* that their morphological characteristics were similar in having: stem erect, cataphylls usually only

subtending peduncles, spadix stipitate, spadix cylindrical, spathe elongate; venation differentiated into primary and secondary veins (Nicolson, 1969; Van 2017; Nguyen 2017). Additionally, our prior work also provided the phylogenetic tree of the species belonging to *Aglaodorum* and *Aglaonema* genera collected from Vietnam using *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF* IGS regions. Accordingly, *Aglaonema cochinchinense* was grouped with *A. simplex* on the phylogenetic tree (Van et al., 2020). In this study, the pairwise alignment of the *matK* regions between these species was conducted (Fig. 2). Accordingly, there were 5 non-homologous positions (158, 166, 389, 457, and 689) between two regions.

The importance of using the DNA barcodes to classify and trace the evolution of Araceae family in Vietnam have been reported by recently studies. For instance, Van et al. (2017b) used *matK* region to construct the phylogenetic tree of *Arisaema* genus in southern Vietnam. It was shown that *Arisaema condaoense*, considered an uncertain species provided by

prior study (Gusman and Gusman, 2006), was a good species endemic to Con Dao National Park of Vietnam (Van et al., 2017b). In addition, Ly et al. (2017) described a new genus from Vietnam, *Vietnamocasia*, using some nuclear and chloroplast regions, including *trnL-F*, *trnK/matK*, *rpl20-rps12* and *phyC* (Ly et al., 2017). Based on the ITS1, FLint2, *rbcL* and *matK* regions, Claudel et al. (2017) deleted the *Pseudodracontium* and confirmed that *Pseudodracontium* belongs to *Amorphophallus* genus. Van et al. (2017a) described a new species, *Alocasia rivularis*, using two molecular regions such as *matK* and *trnL-trnF* IGS. Similarly, based on *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF* IGS regions, Van et al. (2020) transferred *Aglaodorum griffithii* back to *Aglaonema* genus and proposed that it was recognised as a synonym of *Aglaonema griffithii* (Van et al., 2020).

The present study demonstrated that the calcium oxalate crystals were produced in abundance in *Aglaonema cochinchinense* rhizome, both needle shaped and spiny-shaped (raphides). Many Araceae species cause swelling of the lips, throat, and mouth when eaten raw due to their calcium oxalate crystals, especially the needle shaped calcium oxalate crystals (raphides). Therefore, these crystals have been reported as an important indicator of Araceae species (Bradbury & Nixon, 1998; Johns & Kubo, 1988; Paull et al., 1999; Sakai, 1979). Studies also provided the calcium oxalate crystals in two *Aglaonema* species such as *A. modestum* and *A. commutatum* (Genuaf & Hillson, 1985; Saadi & Mondal, 2012). Accordingly, the *A. commutatum* leaf contained both raphide and druse idioblasts. There were two types of the raphide idioblasts in the *A. commutatum* leaf, namely non-defensive raphide and defensive raphide idioblasts. Meanwhile, the druse crystal idioblasts in the leaf of this species consisted of small spherical cells that were distributed throughout the lamina mostly in sub-epidermal regions (Saadi & Mondal, 2012). Similarly, the raphide and druse idioblasts were also found in the leaves of *A. modestum* (Genuaf & Hillson, 1985).

The phytochemical screening of some *Aglaonema* species have been reported by previous studies. It was shown that the ethanol extract of *A. hookerianum* leaves contained several bioactive compounds, including alkaloid, glycoside, tannin, reducing sugar, saponin, and gum (Roy et al., 2011). Similarly, the methanol extracts isolated from the leaf, stem, and root of *A. simplex* possessed reducing sugars, alka-

loids, phenolics, glycosides, steroids, and terpenes (Ismail et al., 2017). The extract from *A. treubii* was found to be rich in several polyhydroxy alkaloids, including 5-O- α -D-glucopyranosyl- α -homonojirimycin, α -3,4-di-epi-homonojirimycin, β -homonojirimycin, α -homonojirimycin, β -homomannojirimycin, 7-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl- α -homonojirimycin, α -homomannojirimycin, and 2(R),5(R)-bis-(hydroxymethyl)-3(R),4(R)-dihydroxypyrrolidine (Asano et al., 1997). In the present study, the ethanol extracts isolated from the rhizomes, roots, flowers, and leaves of *A. cochinchinense* contained various bioactive compounds, including phenolic, tannin, alkaloid, flavonoid, saponin, terpenoid, steroid, and coumarin. In addition, all four organs of this plant also consisted of the significant concentration of the total of triterpene, flavonoid, and polyphenol contents.

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